

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DIDACTIC AND OTHER TYPES OF MODERN GAMES IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: This in the article grow up coming young to generation each different games and psychological actions through education to give and young to the children education in giving them learning science interest them not boring and student young people with with communication in doing speech to form the culture modern style and principles about information given

Key words: educational games, visual material, didactic games, rules-action games, table-printing games. Oral wordy games, game tempo and rhythm, sensory culture.

Sign in. Education the main goal in the field is education and education democratic, humanitarian principles decision find, our people historical traditions and traditions are also universal values based on education - upbringing process content fundamentally change, that's it on purpose pedagogical of teams initiative wide chance open from giving consists of. In children mental activity initially treatment through, after training, games, knowledge to give through done increased Child every always objects, events between will be Always something thing with they know something knowing takes, holds sees, for some reason ear that 's it child world in a way understands All around item and things of children intuition organs, analyzers effect is enough and intuition harvest will be Intuition in children some properties knowing to get help gives In the child mental qualification and skills development, eng simple activity methods subjects check, in them important and important didn't happen characters separate show another subjects with comparison before school education age to the children mental education to give of duties is one Research materials and methodology. Before school education in institutions educational games and their importance. Educational games educational game as of children young features suitable coming games in turn enters Didactic of games important sign in it of the rules existence. in the game game the purpose of the game rules of the game actions in the middle organic contact there is Game purpose game of their actions nature determines Game the rule and the game actions, tasks solution to do and in the game actions done to increase help gives Educational games through to the children new knowledge, concepts giving will go In these games of the child each bilaterally development, knowledge process, sensor culture, speech activity, mental abilities will improve. Game according to the rule compliance do to him action to do game content enriches. Educational in the games natural thing and from items wide is used. Your child day in order educational game for time and allocation of space need Such games training in the process and from the game except at times group or individually will be held. In this game content and result thorough is determined Students with each one in class one how many concepts with the work take will go Har one that's it of the lesson different stages mastery can Har one the concept to understand another one the concept repeat, remember get with take if

you go, it is concept while next concepts explanation for service does Teaching in the process each one study material developed without take will go, this study material from himself after teachable materials to understand for foundation will be Other of understanding absorption process if we look at it, it is one how many of lessons mutually dependent training as a result harvest will be So by doing mathematician concepts harvest to do only one of the lesson in itself harvest without being done, maybe mutually in touch has been one how much lessons transition in the process harvest will be done. Such lessons together lessons we call it a system. That's why for teacher of the subject content opener lessons makes sense in sequence placement need

Main part. Educational in the games the following to the rules action to be done should: take turns effect reach, when asked answer to give, comrades his opinion hear get, game in the process to others interrupt not to give, game the rule perform, own admitting a mistake. Educational in the games of children age, individual characteristics account get it is necessary In the game tempo of the game and rhythm big role plays, too slowly and one plain temp kid a lot waits, very much while fast tempo the children excited puts different to debates take will come Adults by game participants right evaluation important important have Educational of games the following types available: a) item and toys with playable b) table-printing ; d) oral word games. Item and toys with playable games from the first age of the child from, to school to his age to reach until playable game type is considered In this of children imagination, attention game basis organize is enough Them surrounding thing and items, their quality, useful sides about common concept harvest will be In the game playable each one item or a toy his own external apparently have to be, of a thing main symbol separate to know enable to give it is necessary Such games of children of things shape, size, sign, quality about knowledge expands. Table-printing games of children all around about imaginations to determine, one to the system compare, thinking (analysis make, synthesis, generalize, describe) grow enable giver game is a method. This is a game type a) lotto ; b) couple pictures ; d) dominoes; e) labyrinth enters Dictionary enrichment for help giving educational of games types. Educational games. Didactic games educational game as of children young features suitable coming games in turn enters Didactic of games important sign in it of the rules existence. In the game game intention, game rules of the game actions in the middle organic contact there is Game intention game of their actions nature determines. Game the rule and the game actions, tasks solution to do and in the game actions done to increase help will give Discussion didactic games through to the children new knowledge, concepts giving will go In these games of the child each bilaterally development, knowledge process, sensor culture, speech activity, mental abilities will improve. Game according to the rule compliance reach, to him action to do game content enriches Didactic in the games natural thing and from items wide is used. Your child day in order didactic game for time and allocation of space need Such games training in the process and from the game except at times group or individually will be held. In this game content and result thorough is determined. Didactic in the games the following to the rules action to be done need

National people games two to the group divided into: 1. National mobile games. 2. National people games. National mobile games sports with and our people values with related they are centuries during to periods suitable respectively developing, improving, improving bride. It 's the children's physically strong, healthy, brave, persistent, agile, resourceful being in their growth important factor being is considered People national in their games of the nation the

past history, spiritual and cultural development character features, customs, traditions is concentrated.

Conclusion. People national games through the children spiritual, mental, physical, aesthetic in terms of brought up to go in the process in children own Homeland love, his wealth to the value reach, great our ancestors inheritances respect do, national melody and from songs to enjoy feelings also grow coming young in generation endurance, patience, quickness, dexterity, bravery such as personal adjectives forming goes.

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